

A COMPARISON OF MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF JUTE/STYRENE BY VARTM AND HAND-LAY UP METHODS

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1. Introduction

In recent years, as a result of environmental and economic concerns, there has been a growing interest in the use of natural fiber reinforced composites by the academic sector and the industry [1]. Natural fibers have many significant advantages over synthetic fibers. Currently, many types of natural fibers have been investigated for use in plastics, including flax, hemp, jute straw, wood, rice husk, wheat, barley, oats, rye, cane (sugar and bamboo), grass, reeds kenaf, ramie, oil palm empty fruit bunch, sisal, coir, kapok, paper mulberry, banana fiber, pineapple leaf fiber, bamboo etc. Thermoplastics reinforced with special wood fillers are enjoying rapid market growth due to their many advantages, such as light-weight, reasonable strength, and stiffness [2]. Furthermore, natural fibers have been used for the reinforcement of polymeric matrices to produce composites for low-cost applications. The jute is among the best of natural fibers in terms of tensile strength and flexural properties. The physical properties of fiber reinforced composite materials depend on various factors, such as the properties of the fiber and matrix polymer, the interface between the fiber and matrix, and the fiber content. When jute composites were originally made by hand lay-up, it had some minor problems such as remaining air of jute fibers and surface problems. So we made jute composites with styrene resins by VARTM (Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding) instead of the hand lay-up. The VARTM can make jute composites in vacuum. In this study, we compare the VARTM system with original hand lay-up method for tensile and flexure strength from Jute fibers.

2. Experiment

2.1 Materials

Jute fiber as reinforcement in composites was produced in Indonesia but not to a coupling agent. The resin was made of styrene from Japan at U-PICK Co..

2.2 Experimental Methods

As shown in Fig. 1, it was processed by VARTM for jute composites at normal temperature. The VARTM method for production of jute composites is presented below. In the VARTM method, jute fibers on the plate are firstly covered by a vacuum bag, and set in vacuum, created using a vacuum pump. Lastly, jute fiber in vacuum is covered by resin, as air is prevented from entering by a stopper.

Fig. 1. Processing by VARTM for jute composites

Hand lay-up processing of jute composites at normal temperature is shown in Figure 2. In short, hand lay-up just uses the hands and a roller. Each specimen was made by VARTM and hand lay-up in the experiments.

Fig. 2. Processing by hand lay-up for jute composites

Tensile strength indicates the ability of a composite material to withstand forces that pull it apart as well as the capability of the material to stretch prior to failure. A tensile test was conducted using a testing machine in accordance with JIS (Japanese Industrial Standards) K7165 (Standard test method for tensile properties of plastic). Tensile samples (Fig.3.) were prepared by cutting pressed strips into 200 mm length, and overlapping aluminum taps were glued to the sample ends, leaving a parallel-sided exposed sample of 25 mm in length. Testing was conducted at a cross-head speed of 1 mm min⁻¹. At least five samples were tested at each volume fraction.

Fig. 3. Tensile test specimens, fractured tensile specimens

The flexural test measures the force required to bend a beam under 3 point loadings. The data are often used to select materials for parts that will have to support loads without flexing. Flexural modulus is used as an indication of a material’s stiffness when flexed. Flexural strength was calculated according to JIS K7074. The samples were 100 mm long, 15 mm wide and 2 mm thick. The flexural strength was calculated from the expression

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3PL}{2bd^2} \quad (1)$$

for a span to 20mm, where σ_f (MPa) is the stress in the outer fibers at midpoint, P(N) is the load at a given point on the load deflection curve, L(mm) is the support span, b(mm) is width of the test beam, and d(mm) is the depth of tested beam.

Fig. 4. Flexural test specimens, Fractured flexural test specimens

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 presents the weight % of samples for VARTM and hand lay-up. Samples of VARTM are around 47 % resin weight and samples of hand lay-up are 83 % resin weight. The properties of jute composites are affected by resin weight %. Therefore, the composites of lower resin weight % made by VARTM were stronger than that made by hand lay-up.

Table 1. Results of weight % of samples

Jute	Resin Weight [%]
Hand lay-up	83
VARTM	47

Fig. 5 shows the tensile strength for three kinds of samples. Tensile strength values of specimens made by VARTM are about 48~59 MPa, those by hand lay-up are about 23~42 MPa, and samples of resin are 15~36 MPa. Specimens of VARTM are stronger than the others. Also, the tensile strengths of specimens made by VARTM are lower than those of other specimens made by hand lay-up .

Fig. 5. Results of tensile strength

Flexure strength is shown in Fig. 6. Flexure strength values of specimens made by VARTM are 83~96 MPa, and those by hand lay-up are 52~74 MPa, and samples of resin are 28~54 MPa. Specimens of VARTM are stronger than the other specimens in terms of flexure strength. Also, the flexure strengths of specimens made by VARTM are lower than those of the other specimen.

Fig. 6. Results of flexure strength

Fig. 7. Photos of jute composites shapes

Fig. 7. shows the surface of the jute composites as observed through an electron microscope. Both

composites made of hand lay-up and VARTM, respectively, have their particular shapes. When (a) and (b) are compared, (b) made of VARTM is more compact than (a) made of hand lay-up. When (c), (d) are figured?? in their visual shapes, (c) has more void than (d). Both (e) and (g) made by hand lay-up present breaks, whereas (f) and (h) made of VARTM show pullout photos of the surface of a cross section as observed through an electron microscope, which indicates the difference in the specimens between the two methods of processing. The specimens of hand lay-up had more voids and more non-compactness than the specimens of VARTM.

4. Conclusion

Jute composites were successfully developed in this research. The mechanical properties (tensile, flexural) of composites were studied and discussed here. The following conclusions can be drawn from the study

- [1] The comparison of VARTM with hand lay-up for jute composite processing showed that the tensile and flexural strength properties of specimens processed by VARTM were stronger than those processed by hand lay-up.
- [2] The tensile and flexural strengths of jute composites were affected by resin weight %: the lower resin weight % jute composites processed by VARTM was stronger than that processed by hand lay-up.
- [3] Jute composites made by hand lay-up had more defects than VARTM because of no vacuum situation. They had mechanical defects during tensile and flexure test.
- [4] The concentration of jute fiber made by hand lay-up was less than that made by VARTM. High fiber loading was possible with a strong material.
- [5] The jute fiber made by VARTM can be used more efficiently than that made by hand lay-up.

Overall, jute fiber is readily available in the UK and has a large world capacity for market growth in production if demand increases. Good quality composites with very acceptable specific properties can be formed from jute and polyester resins. Thus, this valuable fiber can be used considerably in this country.

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